

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN AXIOLOGICAL AUTONOMY AND AXIOLOGICAL PROFICIENCY

Emil LAZĂR¹

¹University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract

At society level, the quality of the educational-instructive process lies in its capacity to diversify its formative effects for each individual, to enable him to gain inner autonomy and act based on certain self-constructed norms.

The axiological competence is the fissionability of the subject to get closer to the artistic values, to internalize them and turn them into personal goods, but also to recommend them to the others. It consists of value marks to which cultural products relate to.

Such a skill is not only about assimilating some conventions or cultural criteria, but requires that capacity of seeking and discovering new relations between values, consisting of a valuable creativity.

Valuable criteria know a very high diversity, which means that there are things that have value only in the presence of the subject – here and now – and lost it when they are outside the space-time frame.

That's why there's required a permanent self-adjustment of the valuable criteria, in order to obtain maximum effectiveness of the value.

This can be achieved only in the conditions of axiological autonomy, that ensures the spiritual freedom of every individual to have access to values.

That doesn't mean that if we are free, we must accept and take over everything, even if is not related to values such as: good, truth, beauty.

This paper tries to show what it means to be autonomous from the values perspective and which is the role of axiological autonomy in the context of axiological proficiency.

Keywords: values, axiological competency/ proficiency, axiological autonomy

1. Introduction

According to The Dictionary of Philosophy (1978), axiology is the general theory of values, which stresses that value implies a rapport between "something", worthy of appreciation and "someone" able to give appreciation, a rapport between the praised object, and the subject that is praising it.

Petre Andrew, in Philosophy of Value (Andrew, 1977), referring to axiology, writes that the fundamental idea for reconstructing a logic of value is...considering value as the fundamental logical element of our knowledge.

Going forward and trying to deepen the knowledge process of value, he sustains that this is a logical process and gives explanatory theoretical values; the recognition process is practical and results in practical values, capitalized, recommending the necessity of studying the rapports between the practical process of capitalization and, the theoretical process, of knowing the values.

Axiology (according to Cucoş, 1995) designates theory or science of values, and its terminology is given by the Greek word <<axios>>, which means *precious, worthy of being esteemed*.

The human being is the only entity capable of giving value to its own products, and these, aspiring to the status of values, tend towards an existence that makes sense.

This highlights the existence of some individual causes and of some assimilated and internalized norms, which can be updated in any act of appreciation.

The axiological system of reference, to which the person relates to, is formed by the assimilation of the values existing within the society at a certain moment and manifests the openness to everything that constitutes cultural stimuli, which ensures it a virtual functionality.

To avoid the superposition of new valuable guide marks, above the ones already existing, which would lead only to a quantitative growth, is necessary that periodically be achieved a restructuring of “the axiological referential” (Cucos, 2000), so that it ensures an axiological selection of new objectives. We deduce that the axiological system of reference has the quality of operating and functioning, even then when new, unknown aspects, appear.

At society level, the quality of instructive-educational process, consists of its capacity to diversify the formative effects at each individual, to enable him to earn inner autonomy and to act based on some self-built norms.

At hermeneutic level, the subject and the object of knowledge, get involved each other: “the subject invests itself in knowing the object and, in its turn, is determined, in its most subjective position, by the influence that the object has, even before it begins knowing it” (Ricoeur, 1996).

Referring to Heidegger’s hermeneutic circle (Understanding-Interpretation-Discourse), Gadamer (2000) shows that any understanding (text, person), is interpretative, also being the condition of giving sense and

significances. This hermeneutical circle is an anticipated remodeling of the whole, being specific for every knowledge field.

We consider that the process of knowledge combines a cognitive dimension, and also an affective-motivational one, through which the person forms a certain image (knowledge/awareness), about the way it can creatively obtain, the plastic/ suggestive and the figurative.

Through such an approach, based on a certain intelligence (Golu, 2001), the person browses through the stages of a creative process in the way that he/she becomes the subject that feels, gets emotional but, at the same time, recognizes that indirectly participates to this act of creation, becoming a co-author.

This type of capacity takes part in the process of understanding and interpreting the aesthetic values circulated within the literature field, through a series of parameters (Mitrofan & Mitrofan, 1984):

- the adequate perception of symbols, separating the specific mode from the figurative one, in expression;
- fluidity and flexibility in interpretation, namely richer solutions proposed by the person in expressing words and words combination;
- discrimination of the artistic effect, obtained by putting words into a phrase;
- capacity of metaphorical construction, of analogical-symbolic reasoning;
- comprehension and discernment in value hierarchy of artistic products.

This transition of the receiver subject, stresses the mental, cognitive and affective-attitudinal involvement within the axiological construction.

Also, a priority is autonomy and “intrinsic motivation, self-control, self-guidance (Neacșu).

2. Attitudes

2.1. The definitions dynamics

In the attempt to explain social behaviors of people there are more definitions of attitudes, both because of their complexity as well as because of the differences between psychopedagogists' opinions: the disposition to answer selectively to the surrounding objects and phenomena, disposition which, in interaction with situational variables, orientates the subject in action (Vrabie, 1975), way of being or of behaving, often representing a certain conception (DEX, 1998).

The first scientific definition of the attitude concept, available nowadays, is that proposed by G. Allport (1991): a mental and neuropsychological state of preparing the answer, organized by the subject's experience, exerting a direct or dynamic influence on its response to all objects and situations to which it reports to.

We could derive from the above definition, the attitude elements:

- personal experience that can be measured by behavioral manifestations;
- cognitive components of objects, that are associated with positive or negative reactions from the subject;

The analysis of the definition leads us to the conclusion that attitude determines the individual's behavior which is manifested through adapted reactions to the objects that associate and generate attitude.

The reality shows that not always behavior evolves in the same direction and with the same intensity as attitude. This gap can be produced by a number of causes or events:

- the action of more stimuli on the behavior can cause an imbalance manifested through passive, aggressive or indifferent reactions of the subject;
- the action of more attitudes – either complementary or contradictory – reflected in behavior, as a disordered act;
- the distance too great between the moment the subject's attitudes manifest

and the moment when they are noticed and studied, when there can appear modifications.

Taking into account that attitudes represent a way of subject's active reporting to an external reality and that this determines a state of inner tension, we conclude that motivation energetically triggers, guides and supports attitude.

Attitudes, in common language, identifies themselves with the opinions, although the realities they refer to are completely different. Therefore:

- attitudes are the effect of some psychological dispositions; opinions refer to isolated, punctual, specific facts;

- attitudes may be part of behavior (manifested or latent), opinions can be made be disclosed only through language;

- attitude is partially unconscious, opinion is a cognitive fact, of conscience.

The psychological approach of attitude leads us to another correlation, namely that of individual's conviction and belief as judgement, interpretation of the relationship, that includes a set of attitudes concerning an object or a class.

It results that in this case the sphere of conviction is larger, containing also the attitude.

Taking into account that within psychological context attitudes manifest on three levels – cognitive (beliefs), affective (attitude) and behavior (behavioral reactions), we infer that convictions also contain ideas, individual's information on persons, things, situations.

Considering the importance of each component, we mention emotional component as being the central aspect of attitude, cognitive component as the fundamental component of attitude, and the behavioral component as the settlement of active situation (positive or negative) in reference with attitudinal object or with passive interruption (contemplative).

The system of attitudes – values allows the individual, different forms of explicit behavior. When attitudes are subordinated to a single value, the person has a unique orientation in life.

2.2. Functions of attitudes

To stress the way how attitudes, manifest within axiological system, is necessary that their functions to be pointed. or this, we have taken as a model, the classification proposed by Katz (1960):

- **the knowledge function** gives the possibility that through attitudes we evaluate everything that happens around us, according to certain criteria: value of objects, the intensity with which they act upon us, the accessibility degree, motivation;

- **the adaptive function** ensures the acceptance of those objects that are useful to us, that satisfy our needs and the rejection of everything that produce fear and frustration to the subject;

- **the expressive function** is the externalization of individual's inner life according to those values which he considers to be central and by which he differs from the others;

- **the defensive function** of self-shows us how to win and at the same time how to protect our self-esteem in front of every threats – external or internal;

2.3. Factors which determines forming the attitudes

Affective factors

Classical conditioning (the pavlovian one) sustains the idea of conditioning the attitudes, after the S-R formula (a certain stimulus can determine a reaction, which in our case can be an attitude). This synthetic representation of the

conditioned approach of the attitudes, can be completed with the idea that the human subject manifests a behavioral attitude of acceptance or rejection of external stimuli, according to their action, positive or negative on it.

The effect of simple exposure promotes the idea that repeated exposure to a stimulus determines a higher attraction towards that stimulus. This means that the subjects can have a positive/negative attitude towards a repeated stimulus, determined by an unconscious emotional state created by the attractiveness/rejection towards the stimulus; this reasoning lacks cognitive approach of the relationship subject – stimulus – reaction, which leads to the recognition of the emotional dominant of human attitude.

In reality, human attitudes, even if they present themselves in the form of responses towards the action of some stimuli, their affective and emotional side mustn't be seen as absolute, but the recognition of the cognitive fact, that reflects itself within those objective, open, tolerant attitudes of acceptance, cooperation which we find at subjects in relationship with a certain category of stimuli.

Behavioral factors

Operant conditioning is based on the effect of strengthening the answer. This means that if a particular behavior is followed by a positive appreciation, then the probability that this to occur again, increases, and when the appreciation (strengthening) is negative, the chances of its recurrence, diminish. This means that in determining one's own attitudes, the share is owned by both our behavior towards the object, person, event and by the answers we registered when measuring attitudes.

Cognitive factors

In forming human attitudes there is realized an interdependence among all those components bearing information: individuals, social groups, family group, school, media etc.

All these participate directly or indirectly, to building and modelling our attitudes by supplying information about those domains of knowledge with which we have links.

3. Axiological autonomy

Obtaining axiological autonomy is beneficial because it ensures a balance between the diversification of cultures and the individual's freedom to choose its own values.

Axiological autonomy depends on individual's personality, in the sense that there are predispositions towards a democratic individual structure and which, alongside democratic behavior, represent a quality of social group.

Because people are different in their mental structure, it means that this autonomy will oscillate from an individual to another, and this aspect should be taken into account when we speak of education for values and towards values.

The reciprocity between subjects influences axiological autonomy, in the sense that, though autonomy consists in detaching from the others, it requires their freedom to choose for themselves, to not depend on the constrictive power of an individual.

Cultural autonomy mediates axiological autonomy because cultural values being variable, they can suffer changes in time and within different socio-cultural contexts (scientific, artistic, philosophical values, etc. can be converted, at a certain moment, in non-values).

4. The individual's axiological autonomy, mediator factor of the axiological proficiency

Autonomy in this case means that the individual to responsibly attain authentic viable values, to reject mediocrity, phony, to build ways to select new values, without expect from the others counterfeit recipes.

Becoming autonomous and competent from the axiological point of view, human being may understand values and use them in personal and social interest.

As producer and consumer of knowledge, human being must select and join those scientific acquisitions that don't affect its existence and don't generate devastating disasters.

It results the necessity of an axiological rationality and the understanding of it as a coherence, logical and teleological, and of the rules that stand at the base of forming judgments.

Both logical and teleological, put their mark on the action of the human being, in the sense that they determine the way of thinking towards forming convictions, which means that the axiological and the cognitive are the base of our decisions.

We get the idea that axiological reason is the base of our judgments, being a norm of manifestation of the cognitive in values domain (Bârlogeanu, 2002).

4.1 Value

According to Vigano & Parmenteur (1993), as a result of analyzing the value definitions in 39 dictionaries, 24 books and 22 articles, the concept of value is associated with:

- the idea of appreciating a thing, which involves its assessment by the subject that gives it value;
- the idea of satisfying the personal or social needs, which means that value cannot be defined in itself, but by its utility to meet the needs of individuals and society;
- the idea of personality, because choosing values implies all its dimensions: temperament, skills, character, creativity;

These terminological specifications allow us to support the idea that human value is produced in the interaction process between physical world (of matter, of the sensitive, determinations) and the metaphysical world (of spirit, super-sensible, self-reflections).

Currently we sustain that man is the one who appropriates values, but that doesn't mean that the respective action is a simple shift of value from outside to inside the subject.

Assimilating values stresses man's action towards elaborating and producing values, towards transforming something into a quality, into a feature of his.

The essence of value lies within the polar attitude of the subject, namely something that can become a value only as a result of contradictory manifestation from: good/evil, beautiful/ugly, justice/injustice, useful/useless etc.

The conscience of value occurs when a certain void is felt, something that's missing from the structure of reality, when that cannot satisfy subjectivity. That's why man tends to build a mental and material reality that responds to the respective necessities and therefore there arises value as a waiting space (Cucoş, 1995).

The complexity of inner motives determines the axiological complexity that the human being has to manage, solving any potential conflicts that may occur among different levels of axiological and ontological being of the subject.

The values accessible to knowledge, contribute to building an axiological field, on which human existence is based, man being the only being capable of relating to the reality in a projective, attitudinal and preferential way. In this regard, Gordon W. Allport (1991) talked about knowing a person's best if we know what values will be achieved, and building its future is based primarily on personal values; a value is a belief on which a person relies its preferential action.

Whatever the forms under which values occurs (relative/absolute), is man who emphasizes the absolute character of a value or of a good, but his need for the absolute cannot be satisfied, even if the access to knowledge is a way of conceiving and living the absolute.

The sole criterion of the systematization values, is that of predominant elements within values:

- hyperpersonal-logical and mathematical values;
- social-ethical, esthetical, religious/spiritual values (Andrei, 1997).

The idea that emerges from these classifications relates to the fact that value is defined as a relationship between the subject that appreciates and the appreciated object, and its presence is an immanent thing/fact, and is about feeling or reason and may be attributed to a present or potential state of being

Conclusions

There is an axiological competence that consists of values, attitudes and axiological attitudinal factors and which manifests at the values level of a person.

Consistency in its manifestation as axiological competence at a person's level, is mediated by its axiological autonomy, a set of operations and processes of personality in interdependence with its knowledge and affectivity, as internal factors, but also with experiences of learning, living, fellows, other axiology, as external factors.

Autonomy, which implies a personal commitment in situations that requires reflection, decision, behavior, coherence, presents itself as an interdependence between "knowing how to be" and "to know to become", which means that being autonomous is neither the result of a formal learning nor a knowledge accumulation.

It is interesting the association of value with the process of individual's improvement, with the tendency of self-realization, in parallel with the internalization and realization of values, but also with considering them as answering to man's real needs.

In educational activity, rationality is presented in two ways: axiological and instrumental in the sense that when it comes to the share of artistic subjects in plans, programs and textbooks, we frame ourselves in instrumental reason, and when we refer to a certain art (literature), as the one that can achieve the highest category of aesthetic value (sublime), we consider the axiological side.

The education finalities for values are based on subject's autonomy, seen as development potential that needs educational intervention.

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